

EARTH SCIENCES

ОЦЕНКА СОСТОЯНИЯ ПОЧВ В НАХЧЫВАНСКОЙ АВТОНОМНОЙ РЕСПУБЛИКЕ, ИХ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ И ВЛИЯНИЯ ПРИРОДНЫХ И ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКИХ ФАКТОРОВ НА ПОЧВЕННЫЙ ПОКРОВ

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EVALUATION OF SOIL CONDITIONS IN THE NAKHCHIVAN AUTONOMOUS REPUBLIC, THEIR UTILIZATION, AND THE EFFECTS OF NATURAL AND HUMAN FACTORS ON SOIL COVERAGE

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АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье рассматривается ряд природных и антропогенных (техногенных) факторов, обуславливающих состояние, структуру, использование и изменение почвенного покрова Нахчыванской Автономной Республики. Отмечены основные причины деградации почв автономной республики, в том числе негативные последствия геологоразведочных работ, добычи и транспортировки полезных ископаемых, влияющие на экологическую обстановку. В результате были исследованы причины загрязнения почв на данной территории и рассмотрен ряд методов его предотвращения.

ABSTRACT

The article examines several natural and anthropogenic (technogenic) factors that affect the soil ecosystem, structure, use, and change in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. The main causes of soil degradation in the autonomous republic are noted, including the negative consequences of geological exploration, extraction, and transportation of minerals that affect the ecological environment. As a result, the causes of soil pollution in the area were investigated and several methods for prevention were discussed.

Ключевые слова: почва, эрозия, загрязнение, засоление, добыча полезных ископаемых.

Keywords: soil, erosion, pollution, salinization, mining.

The efficient use of soil resources, the preservation of its integrity, and the proper management and control of over pollutants entering the soil are the basis for the protection of soil resources. In recent years, due to the uncontrolled use of natural resources in the territory of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, anthropogenic impacts on the environment has intensified, and technogenic landscapes have developed in the mining and agricultural regions of the autonomous republic. Several environmental issues have arisen in the area, including drastic land cover change, degradation, chemical pollution, erosion, and salinization. Although the area possesses sufficient climate and land resources for agricultural development, the efficient issues use of land resources and their protection have not yet been resolved. Inefficient use of land resources today will negatively impact future supply agricultural production, because when the plants, fruits, and vegetables we eat grow in polluted soil, are absorbed by these product enter the body. Various wastes, organic and inorganic pollutants entering the soil because of anthropogenic impacts have a significant impact on the processes occurring in the soil. Depending on the type and concentration of pollutants entering the soil, the soil's ability

to regenerate becomes impaired. Industrial, manufacturing, and household waste, as well as chemicals used in agriculture, entering the soil as a result of various anthropogenic activities, accumulate in the soil, creating a number of problems, and as a result, the soil's natural regeneration capacity is reduced. High concentrations of chemicals in the soil cause a number of problems, first affecting plant organisms, and subsequently the animals that feed on these plants.[5]

Land degradation occurs as a result of geological exploration, extraction, and transportation of minerals which negatively impacts on the ecological environment. The rich underground and surface resources of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, when used inefficiently, lead to disruption of ecological balance in the region. Despite the development of the mining industry and other industries during the Soviet period, the unplanned exploitation of mineral deposits led to significant environmental pollution. There are deposits of molybdenum, copper-molybdenum in the Paraghachay area, zinc-lead and other minerals in Gumushlu, rock salt, dolomite, travertine, tuff, marbled limestone, gypsum, clay, sand, marl, and gold. Due to long-term exploitation of these areas have become heavily polluted.

River water contaminated with heavy metals from mining waste is commonly for agriculture, daily household needs, and watering livestock. Erosion is one of the main factors contributing to the decline in soil productivity. The lands of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic are among the most severely eroded areas in Azerbaijan. Soils formed under various climatic conditions are either eroded or highly prone to erosion. The primary causes include an arid climate uneven precipitation distribution, anthropogenic impact, and the lack of vegetation cover across large areas of the territory. As a result significant portions of the land have become unsuitable for agriculture and have partially lost their productivity. Climatic elements, geomorphological characteristics, relief features, slope inclination, exposure, and moisture conditions all play an important role in the development of the erosion process. Soil erosion protection includes a system of anti-erosion measures, including organizational-economic strategies, agrotechnical practices, forest-reclamation, and hydrotechnical interventions [7,8].

In the lowland areas of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, developed gray soils cover a specific zone (Boyukduz, foothills, etc.). The humus content in these soils, classified as gray, light gray, and occasionally brown, is between 1.5% and 2%. When wet conditions persist in gray soils for extended periods, they transform into saline and brackish soils. In the Julfa, Babek and Sharur districts of the autonomous republic, which encompass the Arazboyu plain, both natural processes and irrigation practices are not observed. As a result, salinization occurs due to the rise of groundwater to the surface and the influx of saline water washed down from Duzdagh rainfall. Saline soils are widespread in the semi-desert and partially steppe zones of the Araz-bordering plains of Nakhchivan. The factors that contributing and accelerating the salinization process in the region include the relief, climate and lithological composition of the rocks. Due to improper human economic activities, this process has intensified and significantly in scope across the area [2,3].

Photo: Saline soils along the Araz River

During the transition to a new economic policy, the favorable natural and economic conditions, along with the rich recreational and mineral resources of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, have also given rise to several socio-economic challenges. One of the most critical issues is minimizing the environmental damage caused by waste generated during the extraction and processing of natural resources, and repurposing this waste as raw material. The processing and utilization of natural resources in production must be organized in a way that is both ecologically viable and environmentally sustainable. Adequate funding should be allocated for environmental protection measures. Moreover, a comprehensive system of measures for waste reduction and recycling must be developed and effectively implemented. The efficient use of natural resources and environmental protection form a closely interconnected socio-economic and ecological system. Land contamination resulting from mining waste, the construction industry, and other industrial enterprises constitutes a significant component of environmental degradation. Activities such as exploitation, drilling, and processing conducted in mining areas exert both technogenic and anthropogenic impacts on environment. To mitigate the damage caused to these lands, reclamation (recultivation) measures must be implemented. The environmental degradation caused by mining, the extraction of construction materials, and other industrial activities leads to reduced agricultural productivity, disruption of ecological balance, and increased costs for environmental restoration. The expenses associated with the rehabilitation of degraded lands, as well as production-related costs, should be covered by the state budget.

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